

Australian Research Data Commons

Storage and Compute Infrastructure Program

Exploring higher levels of assurance for federated
access to sensitive data

Project Summary

While the project was framed around multi-factor authentication (MFA), identity assurance is as important, if not more important, in establishing a level of trust that a user has a legitimate right to access a service. The term *Strong Authentication* has been adopted by the international federation community to encompass both identity and authentication assurance. Services need the freedom to tune authentication strength in line with risks associated with their systems and the data they contain.

Views on access requirements to sensitive data are varied, but many identity assurance frameworks offer guidelines to help select identity assurance and authentication assurance requirements commensurate with the risk. Institutions may support multiple identity assurance frameworks to work with different stakeholders or industry sectors.

The project found several international federations have deployed strong authentication for a variety of applications. Adoption is patchy as universities struggle to adapt their processes to address the requirements of the assurance frameworks. The underlying technologies are relatively mature with the process and organisational change being the hardest part of implementing strong authentication across federations. Generic services with prevalent use (such as a secure data sharing service or life science platform) could act as a catalyst for widespread adoption.

Project Goal

The project set out to understand the requirements for access to sensitive data and how those requirements might be addressed in a federated environment. The specific questions the project explored were:

1. What specific requirements exist when authenticating researchers for access to sensitive data?
2. How has multi-factor authentication (MFA) been deployed in international contexts? How widely is it used? What is working well? What are the issues?
3. What policies and processes must accompany technology implementations?
4. How well positioned are organisations in Australia's research and education environment (the AAF, institutions and service providers) with respect to policy, process and technology to enable access to sensitive data?

Approach

The project employed primary and secondary research methods to understand how international federations have addressed the problem. This included document reviews and interviews with international federations known to have made progress in implementing MFA. A preliminary assessment of Australian eResearch organisations' ability to work with strong authentication through federations was conducted via a survey in conjunction with CAUDIT.

Activities Undertaken

The following activities were undertaken as part of the project:

- review of a variety of existing documentation including standards, frameworks, and use cases;
- discussion with eResearch sector service providers to identify other activities and requirements involving sensitive data;

- discussion with several universities about current and planned MFA deployments and the drivers for implementation;
- a survey through the CAUDIT's Architecture and Identity and Access Management communities of practice to understand current practices for identity proofing and MFA use; and
- interviews with several overseas federation operators to explore existing deployments involving sensitive data and to understand their approach to securing access.

Participants and Collaborators

AAF acknowledges contributions from the following in developing this report:

- AAF Technical Team;
- Frankie Stevens and Gavin Kennedy (AARNet);
- Stephen Bird (QCIF);
- Hannah Short (CERN, Switzerland);
- Pål Axelsson (SWAMID, Sweden);
- Joe Steele (Jisc, United Kingdom);
- Peter Clijsters (SURFnet, Netherlands);
- Albert Wu (InCommon, USA);
- Andrew Janke and Chris Albone (University of Sydney);
- CAUDIT Identity and Access Management Community of Practice; and
- CAUDIT Architecture Community of Practice.

Outputs

The project generated the following outputs:

- this report;
- a presentation delivered at the ARDC Storage & Compute Infrastructure Summit; and
- a poster.

Findings

What is Sensitive Data?

Data sensitivity is a complex question and the answers are often open to interpretation. The Privacy Act 1988 (Cth)¹ definition of *sensitive information* covers certain kinds of information used by researchers yet excludes other data of varying sensitivity levels. Furthermore, the classification of sensitivity changes with the context in which data is used or accessed. The interpretation of the legislation can also differ between organisations².

¹ Privacy Act 1988: <https://www.legislation.gov.au/Series/C2004A03712>

² Australian Privacy Principles quick reference: <https://www.oaic.gov.au/privacy/australian-privacy-principles/australian-privacy-principles-quick-reference/>

Ultimately the data custodian must determine the level of sensitivity associated with a dataset based on the risks associated with the misuse of the data. Various assurance frameworks help classify risk and provide guidance on appropriate identity proofing and authentication assurance practices.

Principle 1: The data custodian determines the identity proofing and authentication assurance requirements based on the risk and data classification sensitivity.

Relationship to the Five Safes

The Five Safes³ has become a standard framework when dealing with sensitive data for research. Securing access to sensitive data deals with two of the five safes - safe people and safe settings.

Safe people is primarily concerned with ensuring researchers have the appropriate skills and experience to handle and analyse sensitive data. Undertaking an identity proofing process to confirm a researcher is the person they claim to be is a prerequisite. While not explicitly discussed, the Five Safes implies or assumes identity proofing has occurred. Identity proofing may be covered by access protocols for individual data collections within an organisation. Identity proofing becomes more complex in a federated environment where services must rely on third parties to conduct identity proofing.

While services must be sure who is accessing data, the responsibility for identity proofing rests with Registration Authorities (RA) linked to institutional credential service providers (CSP) who facilitate access to sensitive datasets via an Identity Provider. Institutions must ensure identity proofing occurs to the required level and then assert this information as an attribute that a service can interpret and use as part of an authorisation decision.

Safe settings includes data classification, access controls and audit capabilities for use of the data. Multi-factor authentication technologies (such as one time passwords, biometric identification, and hardware tokens) increase the level of authentication assurance to varying degrees. This confirms the registered person has control of their credential and increases the level of trust the service can place in the authentication request.

Principle 2: Strong authentication (identity proofing plus high authentication assurance) means a service can have a higher level of trust in the authentication request.

Strong authentication establishes that:

1. the subscriber's identity has been independently validated (identity proofing); and
2. by virtue of multiple authentication factors, that the authentication request can be trusted to have come from that user (authentication assurance).

Together these components contribute to a *trusted digital identity*. A *trusted digital identity* facilitates strong authentication which enables trust to scale within a federation as the diversity of members and communities increases.

³ Australian Bureau of Statistics - Managing the risk of disclosure: The Five Safes Framework
<https://www.abs.gov.au/ausstats/abs@.nsf/Latestproducts/1160.0Main%20Features4Aug%202017>

Trusted Digital Identity

The term *trusted digital identity* refers to an identity issued using a sufficiently robust identity proofing process together with at least two independent authentication factors. There is an implicit level of trust amongst the Australian research sector organisations. Institutions have reasonably similar processes for issuing credentials and generally trust other institutions to apply processes with similar levels of robustness to their own. This is strengthened through the trust framework of the AAF where all participants have agreed to a common set of terms and conditions in the AAF's Federation Rules.

This level of reciprocal trust may not be present as research activities expand to include new partners (such as government and the health sector). Trusted digital identities will enable researchers to leverage federated authentication to cross these boundaries where the implicit trust relationships are not already established.

Services can use the combination of an identity assurance level and authentication assurance level to determine whether the authentication request is sufficiently trustworthy. Requests that do not reach the required threshold can be handled in several ways:

1. Deny the request and end the transaction;
2. If the request only used a single authentication factor (username and password), initiate a step-up authentication flow to request the user re-authenticate using MFA to increase the level of trust; or
3. Initiate a user registration workflow. Particularly when this is the first time the user has presented to the service, it may be appropriate to push them through a registration workflow. This workflow could be as simple as requesting confirmation of participation from the research project's principal investigator or a more thorough process involving demonstration of sufficient training and experience or police checks.

Assurance Levels

Assurance level frameworks define identity proofing and authentication assurance requirements along a spectrum of increasing trust. Different frameworks have been constructed to meet the contextual needs of different regions and stakeholder groups. Frameworks evolve over time, often borrowing elements from one another. Examples include:

- REFEDS Assurance Framework (RAF) <https://wiki.refeds.org/display/ASS/REFEDS+Assurance+Framework+ver+1.0>. Designed for use by research and education federations in the context of services connected to eduGAIN.
- NIST 800-63-3 Digital Identity Guidelines <https://pages.nist.gov/800-63-3/>. AAF implemented an earlier version of this standard for levels of assurance. The implementation has not kept pace with changes in the standard since federation members have not required assurance beyond the base level of trust.
- Australian Government Trusted Digital Identity Framework (TDIF) <https://www.dta.gov.au/our-projects/digital-identity/join-identity-federation/accreditation-and-onboarding/trusted-digital-identity-framework>. The basis for myGovID and Australia Post's DigitalID, this framework uses many components of NIST 800-63-3 and extends it for local requirements.
- IGTF Generalised Assurance guidelines <https://www.eugridpma.org/guidelines/authn-assurance/igtf-authn-assurance-1.1.pdf>. The

Interoperable Global Trust Federation authentication profiles aim to provide technology agnostic assurance levels for use in a variety of contexts.

- eIDAS European Government eID system

<https://ec.europa.eu/cefdigital/wiki/display/EIDCOMMUNITY/Overview+of+pre-notified+and+notified+eID+schemes+under+eIDAS>. eGovernment focused scheme for the European Union.

These frameworks provide guidance to services about the levels of identity assurance and authentication assurance that should be applied based on the risks associated with the service or underlying data. For example, NIST provide the following criteria as guidance:

- Potential impact of inconvenience, distress, or damage to standing or reputation;
- Potential impact of financial loss;
- Potential impact of harm to agency programs or public interests;
- Potential impact of unauthorized release of sensitive information;
- Potential impact to personal safety; and
- Potential impact of civil or criminal violations.

Service owners rate these risks as low, medium or high and responses determine the appropriate identity proofing and authentication assurance requirements.

Interoperability is an important factor in selecting which framework(s) to adopt. Shared understanding of the meaning of assurance levels within a community is essential. Multiple frameworks may be adopted but each brings additional work to understand the requirements, assess compliance and assert corresponding values. Assurance framework implementations should be minimised but different communities may gravitate toward different frameworks. Service providers may accept assertions from different frameworks if they decide they are equivalent in their specific context. Identity Providers can assert multiple assurance values against several frameworks.

Principle 3: The choice of assurance frameworks should offer as few discrete levels of assurance as is appropriate.

Authentication Assurance through MFA

MFA enables users to demonstrate a higher level of authentication assurance. MFA technologies confirm that a registered user is accessing a service and that the person is in control of the credential.

Multi-factor authentication employs a combination of two or more of the following:

- something you know (a password or a PIN);
- something you have (an access card or token generator);
- something you are (biometric identification such as fingerprint or facial recognition); or
- something you do (such as typing pattern analysis or swipe gestures).

Various options are available in each category with different strengths and limitations. MFA tends to assume a password plus something else but this need not be the case (see *Strong Authentication with WebAuthn*). MFA adoption involves striking the right balance between security and convenience. Organisations will choose to implement different MFA technologies based on various criteria such as inherent security, the risks attached to the data involved, existing technology investments, and budget. The federation must be non-prescriptive about the MFA technologies institutions adopt.

Principle 4: Institutions must be free to adopt MFA technologies that work for them and assert authentication assurance values in line with the framework(s) used by the community.

Principle 5: Multiple frameworks may be supported by SPs and IdPs but communities need to agree which frameworks to adopt.

Strong Authentication with WebAuthn

WebAuthn⁴ enables the creation and use of **strong, attested, scoped**, public key-based credentials by web applications, for the purpose of strongly authenticating users. It allows web applications to trust a strong cryptographic authentication as a credential that is specific to that service.

In the context of WebAuthn, the following definitions apply:

***strong:** authentication is backed by a hardware security module for safe storage of private keys and for cryptographic operations.*

***attested:** authenticators can provide a certificate to help verify that the public key came from an authenticator they trust and not a fraudulent source.*

***scoped:** the key pair is specific to a particular service. For example, a keypair registered for example.edu.au cannot be used at evil-example.edu.au which mitigates phishing attempts.*

WebAuthn combines a site-specific certificate with the native biometric authentication method employed by the local device to achieve strong authentication. Not only is WebAuthn more secure than existing MFA techniques, it also delivers a far superior user experience than one-time password implementations. WebAuthn is likely to become the dominant authentication method in the next few years. Web applications that do not use the WebAuthn login experience will quickly look dated as adoption grows.

Although the standard was only ratified earlier this year, all major desktop and mobile browsers have some degree of WebAuthn support. WebAuthn still has rough edges and behaviour is not always consistent between browsers, but expect rapid adoption as the technology matures.

Strong authentication will no longer be synonymous with a password plus something else. WebAuthn will likely replace the username and password pair as the standard user authentication interaction.

The Australian Context

Higher education have embraced MFA in recent years though adoption has primarily come as a response to cyber security incidents. Stronger authentication is now a necessity, not only to protect sensitive data but also to protect organisations and people from reputational damage due to malicious actors⁵.

The following factors were identified as drivers for higher levels of assurance in research and education:

- growth in cyber security threats;
- increasing use of sensitive data in research;

⁴ Web Authentication API (WebAuthn) is a specification written by the W3C and FIDO. <https://webauthn.guide/>

⁵ Office of the Australian Information Commissioner - Notifiable Data Breaches Statistics Report: 1 April to 30 June 2019:

<https://www.oaic.gov.au/privacy/notifiable-data-breaches/notifiable-data-breaches-statistics-report-1-april-to-30-june-2019/>

- risks associated with person and institutional loss or damage;
- legislation and policy; and
- mitigation against human error.

Together with CAUDIT, the project surveyed institutions in Australia and New Zealand about their:

1. existing and planned support for MFA technologies;
2. current practices for identity proofing; and
3. integration of this information with their identity management systems and their ability to assert this through the federation.

The MFA survey received 40 responses and the identity proofing survey received 20 from CAUDIT members in Australia and New Zealand. Key insights include:

- Most universities have deployed MFA for at least a subset of their user base;
- Smartphone-based applications are the most common with Microsoft Authenticator and Duo dominating;
- Cyber threat mitigation is the main driver for adoption of MFA; and
- a small number of universities have robust identity proofing in place. A smaller number provide this information to identity management systems so that it could be asserted through the federation.
- For most universities, practices vary by departments and stakeholder groups.

Appendix A and B provide selected highlights from the survey analysis.

International Deployments

There are a number of international examples from which Australia can learn. The project engaged with several international federation operators to identify existing use cases.

CERN - Switzerland

CERN have implemented strong identity assurance and authentication assurance for all users. In-person identity verification is performed against passports or other government identity documentation for all credentials issued by CERN. During the identity verification process the user's smartphone authenticator application is linked to their CERN credential. Alternatively, a Yubikey can be issued to the user for authentication assurance.

Significant use of command line resources means local accounts are usually necessary. Consequently, CERN issue credentials for all visiting researchers. This is expected to change in coming years since R&E federations are now in a better position to assert strong authentication. CERN will move to federated authentication and cease issuing credentials to people who are not CERN employees.

Application owners make a decision about authentication assurance levels based on the risks associated with the application and data. Higher-risk systems require MFA while standard authentication is sufficient for many systems.

Even with this robust credential process, system access is not automatic. A research project's chief investigator must approve access once validated credentials are issued.

SWAMID - Sweden

The Swedish federation (SWAMID) has supported strong authentication with in-person passport verification and MFA for approximately 18 months. Assurance level profiles enable systems to request anything from a unique (but not necessarily identifiable) user through to identities validated against government records and linked to hardware tokens. A system that stores medical information about students with disabilities for financial and other aid requires the strongest authentication profile.

Assurance levels⁶ are aligned with NIST 800-63. SWAMID are revising the profile definitions based on practical experience. The initial deployment provided more levels than were needed for practical use.

Technical hurdles have been relatively easy to clear and change management has been the biggest challenge. Many federation members employ credential issuing practices that do not meet the minimum standard for higher assurance levels. Until these processes change within the universities, access to systems requiring higher assurance is not available.

Jisc - United Kingdom

Services in the UK federation are heavily skewed toward educational resources and publisher content in particular. Consequently, there has not been a great need for MFA within the federation. Some universities have adopted MFA internally and this is largely a reactive response to security incidents.

The UK government's Verify program aims to create an identity assurance program for use across government and other agencies. The government is looking to tap into university records through Jisc as one data source for validating identity.

SURFnet - The Netherlands

The Dutch NREN (SURFnet) has operated SURFsecureID⁷ since 2016 and has approximately 70 cloud services protected by MFA. SURFsecureID allows members of the Netherlands education and research sector to access resources via SURFnet's managed MFA solution.

Self registration of an MFA token or application is optional. Registration is supported by an in-person visit by the user to their home institution support desk to enable their MFA registration. The MFA registration includes an identity validation process.

SURFsecureID is used for both cloud services linked to a user's SURFconext account and for third party services. Compliance with GDPR laws has been a driver for strong authentication in many European organisations.

⁶ SWAMID Identity Assurance Level 1 Profile:

<https://www.sunet.se/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/SWAMID-Identity-Assurance-Level-1-Profile-v2.0-FINAL.pdf> and <https://www.sunet.se/swamid/policy/a1/>

SWAMID Identity Assurance Level 2 Profile:

<https://www.sunet.se/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/SWAMID-Person-Proofed-Multi-Factor-Profile.pdf> and <https://www.sunet.se/swamid/policy/a2/>

⁷ SURFsecureID: <https://www.surf.nl/surfsecureid-diensten-extra-beveiligen-met-tweefactorauthenticatie>

InCommon - United States of America

MFA is relatively widespread across US universities but adoption is almost entirely driven as a response to attempted or actual information security breaches. InCommon negotiated a sector deal with Duo before it was acquired by Cisco and Duo dominates MFA deployments in the US higher education market. The requirement for MFA use varies across institutes, ranging from mandatory use for all staff and students through to opt-in at the choice of the end user.

There is no consistent or widely adopted assurance framework in the US federation. The InCommon Assurance Program⁸ attempted to align with the NIST framework but only a handful of organisations have adopted it. Services rarely ask for any identity proofing, so InCommon have taken a light-touch approach to identity proofing. Institutions tend to apply stronger identity proofing processes only when staff request privileged access to HR and financial systems.

Analysis and/or Emerging Themes

A number of emerging themes were identified throughout the project:

- Implementing MFA without addressing identity validation provides limited value in the context of identity federations;
- Federations must accommodate (virtually) any MFA technologies the institutions adopt. Identity providers must signal compliance with agreed strong authentication profiles without service providers prescribing the technology solutions to be used;
- WebAuthn is likely to be disruptive for existing MFA approaches but deliver a superior user experience while strengthening security
- Service Providers must undertake a risk assessment about the data and set appropriate requirements for the level of assurance sought. As with authentication and access decisions, the service must have flexibility to decide the rules for access to the resource;
- Identity Providers must implement methods to conduct identity proofing activities, maintain records and assert this through the federation; and
- the sector must work together to define use cases and adopt an appropriate assurance level framework.

Next Steps

The project has identified a number of high level actions to move forward with strong authentication in the Australian eResearch sector. The funding arrangements and mechanics of these activities are still to be determined.

For the Australian Access Federation

- Collect identity assurance and authentication assurance use cases for a range of research activities;
- Evaluate candidate assurance frameworks to support these use cases; and
- Work with stakeholders (CAUDIT, eResearch/DVCR, Universities Australia, ARDC, DDeRP and NCRIS, Government, Health and others) to select the most appropriate framework(s);
- Develop the value proposition in conjunction with stakeholders;

⁸ InCommon Assurance Program: <http://detective.internet2.edu/assurance/index.html>

- Develop and execute a comprehensive communication and support program; and
- Work closely with the sector in Implementing the new framework.

For Identity Providers (Institutions)

- Begin planning for stronger identity assurance for cohorts where it is most important;
- Understand the requirements for identity assurance levels and authentication assurance levels;
- Implement identity verification processes when issuing credentials;
- Link records about this data to the identity management systems;
- Develop and execute a comprehensive communication and support program; and
- Assert identity assurance and authentication assurance levels as attributes in the federation.

For Service Providers (eResearch services)

- Assess the risks associated with systems and the data they contain; and
- Use the guidance offered by the chosen assurance frameworks to require appropriate assurance from Identity Providers.

Issues and Barriers to Goals

- Identity Providers appear to have the most work ahead. Some institutions are already in a good position. For others, changing processes and systems to enable strong authentication will be a long road;
- The inconvenience caused by adding MFA has been a barrier for many institutions - particularly when considering deployment across all cohorts. Recent prominent security incidents in the sector have helped illuminate the need for stronger authentication. WebAuthn promises to improve the user experience and reduce inconvenience;
- Any MFA is better than none. However, some MFA technologies are less secure than others eg: SMS OTP
- Education, support and ease of use are critical to user adoption and acceptance; and
- Applying strong authentication to high risk systems and users is a valid approach. It does not have to be one size fits all.

Glossary

Australian Privacy Act

The Australian Privacy Act was drafted as a consequence of Australia's obligations under international treaties, obligations and associated concerns. The Privacy Act governs the way in which business entities and federal government agencies must handle personal information. State and Northern Territory governments, their agencies and authorities are only bound to a limited extent by the Privacy Act, but may be governed by the regulations made under the Act; or a State's own privacy legislation. The various regimes contain exclusions and exceptions which influence the application of legislation⁹ in general

Authentication

The process of presenting one or more credential secrets to verify or confirm a digital identity in an online transaction.

Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI)

Cross-institutional infrastructure providing federated authentication and authorisation among participating organisations.

Authentication Assurance

In any online transaction, the ability to determine that an authentication assertion made by an entity during an authentication event can be trusted.

Authentication Assurance Level (AAL)

Indicates the level of risk or certainty which can be associated (or ascribed) to an authentication event and that the entity presenting the credential has full control of the credential.

Authentication Factors

Secrets employed in an authentication event to demonstrate that an entity has control of the digital identity linked to the entity. These factors are commonly grouped as follows:

- A secret or something only the entity knows (a password or a PIN)
- An object which is, or generates, or receives a secret (an access card or token generator or an SMS one-time pin)
- A distinguishing personal characteristic (biometric identification such as fingerprint or facial recognition)
- A distinguishing personal action (such as typing pattern analysis or swipe gesture)

A factor from any one group should be derived independently of the other factors

⁹ Overview Of Privacy Law In Australia: <https://hallandwilcox.com.au/thinking/overview-of-privacy-law-in-australia/>

Credentials

In an authentication context, credentials represents the tokens or secrets provided by an entity (subscriber) arising from an authentication event to enable access to a service. This establishes an entity relationship between digital identity and a service provider.

In an identity validation context, credentials are the real world identity documents which support an entity's assertion of personal attributes and characteristics. This establishes an entity relationship between a person or organisational entity and a digital identity. This context applies during identity validation.

Credential Service Provider (CSP)

A trusted organisation which issues electronic credentials or security tokens to entities (subscribers) for use in authentication events. A CSP may be an independent third party, or may issue credentials for its own entities.

Digital identity

Information used by a computer system to represent an entity which can include online activity. A digital identity contains aspects of a civil or personal identity information related or used to describe an entity.

Entity

A person, organisation, application or device which possess characteristics or properties which represent distinct real world subjects.

Enrolment

The process through which an applicant applies to become a subscriber of a CSP and the CSP validates the applicant's identity.

Five Safes Framework

A policy and procedure framework for the classification of sensitive data to determine suitable access controls for research access. The framework assists in the decisions required for the effective use of data which is confidential or sensitive; and intends to address the following aspects of data management decisions:

- Projects
- People
- Settings
- Data
- Outputs

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The European Union's GDPR regulation aims to protect personal data, or information relating to an identifiable person who can be directly or indirectly identified in particular by reference to an identifier. This definition provides for a wide range of personal identifiers to constitute personal data, including name, identification number, location data or online identifier, reflecting changes in technology and the way organisations collect information about people. The regulation also protects European citizens' data outside

the European Union and applies to all companies processing personal data regardless of a company's location.

Identity

A set of attributes which describe an entity or subject within a given context.

Identity assurance

In an online transaction, the ability to determine that a claim to an identity made by an entity can be trusted.

Identity Assurance Level (IAL)

Indicates the level of risk or certainty which can be associated (or ascribed) to an identity assertion, and that the assertion represents a real entity. The assertion may be opaque and NOT transfer any identifying information on the submitting entity.

Identity Federation

An organisation primarily tasked with coordinating and managing the technology to exchange authentication and identity assertions; and establishing real world trust relationships between participants.

Identity Validation

The policy and process employed to verify those personal attributes asserted by an individual are correct and accurate, and are contained within the digital identity.

Identity Proofing

See *Identity validation*.

Levels of Assurance (LoA)

The level of assurance is a measure of the strength and rigor of the identity proofing process, the strength of the token used to authenticate the identity claim, and the management processes the identity provider applies to it. The term LoA is replaced by the NIST terms Authentication Assurance Level (AAL), Identity Assurance Level (IAL) and Federation Assurance Level (FAL) to address differences in risk in the different aspects of assurance.

Multi-factor Authentication (MFA)

The request for two or more authentication factors during an authentication event initiated by an entity. Nominally, the requested factors are from independent categories. Implementations typically request a secret for one of the factors.

Registration Authority (RA)

A trusted entity tasked with enrolling subscribers. The tasks undertaken normally include evaluating an entity's real world credentials and ensuring an entity's associated digital identity reflects the entity's real world credentials.

Sensitive Data

Information that, if disclosed or modified without authorisation, would have severe adverse effect on the operations, assets, or reputation of an individual or an organisation.

Strong Authentication

Strong Authentication provides a high level of confidence to a service that a user is who that person claims to be and has control of the credential used to access the services. This is achieved by the combination of high levels of identity assurance and authentication assurance.

Social Engineering

The act of deceiving an individual into revealing sensitive information, obtaining unauthorized access, or committing fraud by associating with the individual to gain confidence and trust.

Subscriber

A party who has received a credential or authenticator from a CSP.

Personal Identification Number (PIN)

A memorized secret typically consisting of only decimal digits.

WebAuthn

The Web Authentication API (also known as WebAuthn) is a specification written by the W3C and FIDO, with the participation of Google, Mozilla, Microsoft, Yubico, and others. The API allows servers to register and authenticate users using public key cryptography instead of a password.

Report prepared by: John Scullen and Patrick Carnuccio (Australian Access Federation)

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Appendix A - MFA Survey Highlights

The MFA survey received 40 responses from 29 unique organisations.

Q2. Has your institution deployed MFA?

Q6. Of those institutions who have, or are intending to adopt MFA, which cohort(s) of users are/will be enabled?

User Cohort	Count
All staff and students	8
All staff	22
IT Staff	9
Identified 'privileged users'	10
Senior Management	7
Contractors	8
Corporate Services Staff	6
Academics	4
Other	9

Q9. Which factors are the primary drivers for MFA adoption (eg. security incidents within your organisation, internal risk and compliance committees, cyber-security activities etc)?

Responses mostly were similar and related to the topics of:

- Mitigating cyber threat activities (phishing in particular)
- Increasing the maturity of cyber posture
- ASD compliance
- Overall good practice

Appendix B - Identity Validation Policy / Process Survey Highlights

The identity validation policy and process survey received 20 responses from 18 unique organisations.

Q2. Does your organisation perform identity validation or identity proofing?

Q4. For organisations that perform identity validation, does the process record successful validation in a non-repudiable manner?

Q5. For departments in your organisation which perform identity validation, is the status of a (successfully) validated identity (not the identity documentation) shared within the organisation's identity management systems?

Q7. For organisations that perform identity validation or identity proofing, which requisites are necessary for the identity validation process?

